

On an Inductive Method for the Study of Natural Products. Part I. The Naturally Occurring Anthraquinone Derivatives.

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Although a large number of anthraquinone derivatives present in nature have been known for a long time, it is only during recent years that the constitutions of some of the most important members of this group have been determined with certainty. We would refer to the synthesis of chrysophanic acid by Eder and Widmer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1922, 5, 3) and of emodin by the same authors (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1923, 6, 966) and also by Jacobson and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 1312), of morindone by Jacobson and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 46, 2788) and of rubiadin by Mitter and Gupta (this *Journal*, 1928, 5, 25).

An examination of these and other naturally occurring anthraquinone derivatives reveals the fact that only certain definite configuration of methyl and hydroxyl groups are present in them and also that it is possible to classify them under four distinct heads.

The following empirical laws are found to hold good in the case of anthraquinone derivatives present in plants.

(1) No naturally occurring anthraquinone derivative contains more than four substituent groups in the two benzene nuclei, namely, not more than *one* methyl (or carboxyl or carbinol group) which, if present, always occupies a β position, and not more than *three* hydroxyl groups.

(2) The substances containing the maximum number of substituents form the fundamental types and the other anthraquinone derivatives occurring in the same plant are all derived from this fundamental type being either oxidation or reduction or etherification etc., products of the same. The fundamental types are therefore also derivable by superposing the formulæ of associated anthraquinones.

(3) Of the four substituents two (including the methyl or carboxyl or carbinol group, if present) occupy β -positions and the other two occupy α -positions.

(4) If both the β -substituents are in one ring the other groups also occur in the same ring or in other words, a homonuclear type is formed. If both the β -substituents are OH groups they must occur in the same ring.

(5) If the β -substituents are in different rings the α -substituents are distributed in such a way as to produce a symmetrical configuration.

As no two types have three groups in common, it is possible by examining any one naturally occurring anthraquinone containing three substituents (sometimes even two substituents) to determine the fundamental type from which this particular substance and *all the other anthraquinone derivatives associated with it* have been derived.

Starting from anthraquinone we get by substituting two β -positions by two hydroxyl groups or by one hydroxyl and one methyl group the following types:—

From these four β -substituted products we can derive the four fundamental types of naturally occurring anthraquinones—two homonuclear and two heteronuclear.

These exhaust, barring a few apparent exceptions which we hope to be able to show also conform to the above four categories—the anthraquinone derivatives occurring among plant products.

As regards the relative position of the hydroxyl groups it is interesting to note that the alizarin grouping (1:2) can occur in three out of the four fundamental types:—Chayroot, madder and morindone.

It is also interesting to note that while the 1:6-grouping is common both to the morindone and the emodin types, the anthrarufin (1:5)-grouping is present only in the morindone type while the chrysazin grouping (1:8) is present only in the emodin type. The diagnostic value of these observations will be apparent later on.

Type I (Chayroot type).

Our knowledge about this group is derived from the works of A. G. Perkin and Hummel (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1893, 63, 1160 ; 1895 67, 817). The substances isolated from chayroot are 2-oxyanthraquinone, alizarin, alizarin-*O*-methyl ether, anthragallol-1 : 2-dimethyl ether, anthragallol-1:3-dimethyl ether and hystazarin monomethyl ether. They may be all regarded as derived from anthragallol by permutation and combination of the hydroxyl groups, at least one β standing hydroxyl group, being present. Another way of looking at the products would be to consider them as members of oxidation and reduction chains as follows:—

So far, only derivatives of these four substances have been found in chayroot.

It is interesting to note that chayroot, the root of *Oldenlandia umbellata* (Linn) *Rubiaceæ*, although belonging to the same natural order as madder does not contain any anthraquinone derivative with a methyl group in the nucleus. It is an illustration of the non-superposability of the types, without which the theory would at once fall to the ground.

Type II (Madder type).

The anthraquinone derivatives of the madder type have been very largely investigated and a complete bibliography up to 1918 will be found in "The Natural Organic Colouring Matters" by Perkin and Everest (pp. 35). All the members of this type (with the exception of Munjisthin which we are now investigating) may be derived from 3-methylpurpurin, a substance which is probably present in madder but which we have been unable, up to the present moment in isolating from it, although attempts are being made in that direction. They can also be regarded as members of oxidation and reduction chains.

As already indicated, the real value of this hypothesis would depend on the non-existence of mixed types. There are on record two cases which are apparent exceptions to this rule. Hugo Muller (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 968) had found traces of alizarin in rhubarb. As he had investigated residues which had accumulated in course of a long series of investigations extending over many years and only obtained minute traces of alizarin, the chances of possible contamination of the starting materials with alizarin containing materials cannot be altogether ignored. In the second place we have Simonsen's observation about the presence of rubiadin monomethyl ether in *Morinda citrifolia* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 561) along with morindone (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 113, 766).

As against this we have the observation of Barrowcliff and Tutin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 1909) who had found, in the root of *Morinda longiflora*, alizarin monomethyl ether and rubiadin monomethyl ether but no morindone. Whether the case observed by Simonsen is really an exception to the general rule formulated before or whether as Simonsen observes that "it is possible that the latter (*Morinda longiflora*) might at some period of its growth contain morindin, since the quantity of glucoside appears to vary with the age of the bark (*loc. cit.*), is difficult to say at the present moment.

(3) In the emodin group, the following substances are known:—

It will be observed that they are all derivable from one fundamental type. We are now engaged in the synthesis of other anthraquinone derivatives of the same type containing the same or a smaller number of groups with a view to identifying some of the lesser known products accompanying emodin.

(4) In the morindone group, the only substance of which the constitution is definitely known is morindone itself. From the foregoing it would be reasonable to expect that the products accompanying morindone would be related to it in the same way as the anthraquinones of the other three types to the fundamental types. Thus, a substance whose analytical data and properties agree with that of a dihydroxy-derivative of a methyl anthraquinone would be one of the following :—

The first of these compounds has been synthesised by Simonsen and Rau (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1340). It melts at 281° and its acetyl derivative melts at 212°.

In their investigation of Mang-Koudu, the root bark of *Morinda umbellata*, Perkin and Hummel (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1894, 65, 851), describe the presence of a substance of m. p. 281° the analysis of which agrees more or less with that of dihydroxymethylanthraquinone. (C, 69·31; H, 4·09 instead of C, 70·86; H, 3·93 per cent.).

Oesterle and Tisza (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1908, 246, 150), have isolated from the root bark of *Morinda citrifolia* small quantity of a substance to which they gave the name Soranji-diol. It melted at 277°. The analysis of the acetyl derivative (m. p. 230°) agrees with that of di-acetoxy-methylanthraquinone although that of the hydrolysis product is somewhat divergent (C, 72·17; H, 4·04 instead of C, 70·86; H, 3·93 per cent.).

From the above we may reasonably conclude that the compound isolated by Perkin and Hummel and the Soranji-diol of Oesterle and Tisza was 2:5-dihydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone.

Oesterle and Tisza (*loc. cit.*) have found in *Morinda citrifolia* another dihydroxy-methylanthraquinone which they named Morindadiol dissolving in alkalis with an orange-red colour and in sulphuric acid with a cherry-red colour. It melted at 244° and the acetyl derivative melted at 229°.

The product (2), 1:5-dihydroxy-6-methylanthraquinone which we have synthesised, gives identical colour reaction and its acetyl derivative melts at 230°. But the hydrolysis product melts at 190°.

We have also synthesised (3) by condensing hemipinic anhydride with toluene in presence of aluminium chloride and treating the toluoylbenzoic acid so formed with sulphuric acid. We found that in the formation of toluoyl benzoic acid a methyl group is split off, thereby confirming Lagodzinski's supposition that in the condensation of hemipinic anhydride with benzene a hydroxy methoxy benzoyl benzoic acid is formed (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1427) although it has been sometimes held that the splitting up of the methoxyl group takes place at the time of ring closing with sulphuric acid (Bentley and Weizmann, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 435).

We have also assumed that in this condensation it is the CO-group next to the methoxyl groups which reacts and that the ketone group enters in *p*-position to the methyl group so that the resulting compound has formula (1) and not formula (2).

This has been demonstrated by Bistrzycki and Yssel de Schepper in the case of condensation of hemipinic anhydride with anisol (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 2800; *vide* also Simonsen and Rau, (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1339 (*foot-note*)). The formation of a compound of formula (1) in the first instance would explain the subsequent splitting off of the methyl group as it is well known that the presence of CO groups in *ortho*-position renders the methoxyl groups unstable. The anthraquinone melts at 220° and its acetyl derivative melts at 190°. But it does not agree with any natural product isolated so far.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1:5-Dimethoxy-6-methyl-anthraquinone.

1:5-Dinitro-6-methylanthraquinone was prepared according to the method of Eder, Widmer and Bütler by nitrating β -methyl-anthraquinone with nitric acid (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, 7, 341). After separation from 1:8-dinitro-compound and recrystallisation from pyridine it melted at 335°. The 1:5-dinitro compound was then converted into 1:5-dimethoxy-6-methyl anthraquinone by the method of Kaufler (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 65). The dimethoxy compound crystallised from glacial acetic acid melted at 176°-177°.

(Found: C, 72.19; H, 4.91; OMe, 21.6. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires
 \leftarrow
 C, 72.34; H, 4.96; 2 OMe, 21.9 per cent.)
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Demethylation of 1:5-Dimethoxy-6-methyl-anthraquinone.

The dimethoxy compound (0.5 g.) was dissolved in some 25 c.c. glacial acetic acid saturated with HCl acid gas and heated in a sealed tube for 2 hours at 190°-200°. After cooling the contents were transferred to a beaker by washing with water, boiled and after filtration the yellow mass dissolved in very dilute alkali to a red solution which on acidification gave a yellow precipitate. Recrystallised from glacial acetic acid it melted at 190°. (Found: C, 70.57; H, 4.07. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70.86; H, 3.93 per cent.)

Acetyl derivative of 1:5-Dihydroxy-6-methyl-anthraquinone.

It was prepared in the usual way and crystallised from alcohol; m.p. 230°. (Found: C, 67.16; H, 4.21. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.45; H, 4.14 per cent.)

On deacetylation a product was obtained which on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid was found to melt at 190°.

3-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-2-p-toluoyl-benzoic acid.

Hemipinic anhydride (10 g.) was suspended in 200 c.c. toluene and to this anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (20 g.) was added in small portions

and then the flask containing the mass was heated on water-bath at 45-55° for 5 hours. The flask was then cooled in ice while dilute HCl (200 c.c.) was added and the toluene left in excess was removed by means of steam. The crude benzoylbenzoic acid obtained was boiled with CaCO₃, filtered and on acidifying the filtrate, white crystals of the benzoylbenzoic acid appeared (yield, 7 gms). Recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, 5 gm. of the acid m.p. 175-76° were obtained. (Found: C, 67.54; H, 4.83. C₁₆H₁₄O₃ requires C, 67.13; H, 4.89 per cent. Found: OMe, 10.13. C₁₅H₁₁O₄ (OCH₃) requires OMe, 10.83 per cent.).

Preparation of 1-Hydroxy-2-methoxy-6-methylanthraquinone.

To the benzoylbenzoic acid (5 g.) was added boric acid (5 g.) and sulphuric acid (10 g., sp. gr. 1.84). To the mixture were then added 50 gm. of fuming sulphuric acid (20% SO₃) and heated on the water-bath for 3 hours. It was then poured into ice when a brown mass was obtained. This was then boiled with a dilute solution of sodium carbonate and filtered. From the filtrate on acidification a gram of benzoylbenzoic acid was recovered. The crude anthraquinone weighed about 4 gm. On crystallisation from glacial acetic acid 3 gm. of orange yellow crystals of the anthraquinone, m.p. 200°, were obtained. (Found: C, 72.06; H, 4.53. C₁₆H₁₂O₄ requires C, 71.64; H, 4.48; ger cent.).

Acetyl derivative—From the 1-hydroxy-2-methoxy-6-methylanthraquinone the acetyl derivative was prepared in the usual way. Crystallised from absolute alcohol it melted at 170°. (Found: C, 69.65; H, 4.45. C₁₈H₁₄O₅ requires C, 69.68; H, 4.52 per cent.)

Demethylation of 1-Hydroxy-2-methoxy-6-methyl anthraquinone.

Preparation of 6-Methylalizarin.

One gram of the anthraquinone was mixed with 2 gm. of finely powdered AlCl₃ and heated to 220° in course of one hour and then kept at this temperature for half an hour. When cooled, the reaction mixture was carefully transferred to a beaker with water and then it was boiled with a few c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid till brown flakes appeared. It was filtered, dissolved in one per cent potassium hydroxide solution, filtered and the filtrate acidified when

thick yellow flakes appeared. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid the 6-methylalizarin obtained melted at 220°. (Found: C, 70·46 ; H, 4·20. $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 70·86 ; H, 3·93 per cent.)

Acetyl derivative.

It was prepared in the usual way. Crystallised from alcohol it melted at 190°. (Found: C, 67·22; H, 4·35. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67·45 ; H, 4·14 per cent.).

On deacetylation and sublimation of the product the m.p. was found to be 220°.

Further experiments are in progress.

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Received December 2, 1928.